

**INDIVIDUAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDENTS AND
THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN THE PROCESS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE
ACQUISITION**

Mardiyeva Shaxnoza Amirovna

SamSIFL, Associate Professor of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology

mardiyevashaxnoza19820111@gmail.com

Tukxtameshov Abdurakhmon

SamSIFL, Master's student in Foreign

Language and Literature

Аннотация: В данной статье с научно-педагогической точки зрения анализируются индивидуальные психологические особенности учащихся и их значение в процессе изучения иностранного языка. В исследовании раскрывается влияние таких индивидуальных особенностей, как тип темперамента, мотивация, интерес, память, мышление, внимание, эмоциональное состояние и коммуникативные способности, на эффективность усвоения языка. Также рассматриваются педагогические возможности применения индивидуального подхода в процессе обучения иностранному языку, а также вопросы использования эффективных методов и технологий.

Ключевые слова: индивидуальные психологические особенности, иностранный язык, мотивация, темперамент, коммуникативная компетенция, изучение языка, индивидуальный подход, эффективность обучения.

Annotation: This article analyzes students' individual psychological characteristics and their significance in the process of foreign language learning from a scientific and pedagogical perspective. The study highlights the influence of such individual characteristics as temperament type, motivation, interests, memory, thinking, attention, emotional state, and communicative abilities on the effectiveness of language acquisition. In addition, the pedagogical possibilities of applying an individual approach in the language teaching process, as well as the use of effective methods and technologies, are discussed.

Keywords: Individual psychological characteristics, foreign language, motivation, temperament, communicative competence, language learning, individual approach, educational effectiveness.

Introduction:

The effectiveness of the educational process is largely determined by taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of students. In modern pedagogy and psychology, the concept of student-centered education is considered one of the priority areas.

The development of the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the support of students' individual capabilities have been designated as priority areas of state policy. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" states: "The main principles of state policy in the field of education are the humane and democratic nature of education, the creation of conditions for obtaining education in accordance with the abilities and needs of students" [1].

This situation indicates the need to organize the educational process taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of students.

Also, in the decisions put forward by Shavkat Mirziyoyev to improve the system of teaching foreign languages, the perfect study of foreign languages by young people is defined as an important strategic task. Including: "Radical improvement of the foreign language teaching system using modern pedagogical and information-communication technologies" tasks as one of the important directions of state policy [2].

This approach requires the organization of the educational process taking into account the age, psychological, and individual characteristics of students. This is because psychological factors such as motivation, attention, memory, temperament, and communicative activity play an important role in the language learning process.

Thus, in the legal and regulatory documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan on education, special attention is paid to the issues of student-centered education, an individual approach, and taking into account the psychological characteristics of students, which is an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of foreign language teaching. Especially in the process of learning a foreign language, the individual characteristics of students, such as temperament, character, motivation, abilities, attention, memory, and thinking, are of great importance. This is because every student possesses unique psychological capabilities for receiving, processing, and implementing information into practice.

Individual psychological characteristics consist of each individual's unique mental, emotional, and behavioral traits, which constitute their personality. These characteristics are

¹. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education." – Tashkent, 2020.

². Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012, No. PP-1875 "On measures to further improve the system of studying foreign languages."

reflected in a person's self-perception, attitude toward the surrounding world, relationships with others, and behavior in various situations. Identifying and accounting for individual psychological characteristics helps make the process of orientation to modern professions effective. Individual characteristics of students include factors such as their character, abilities, interests, temperament, and talents. These aspects determine the uniqueness of each individual and are of great importance in the process of choosing a profession. Psychological characteristics include elements such as the student's emotional state, motivation, decision-making ability, and stress resistance.

As the psychologist Lev Vygotsky noted, "education is the primary factor driving personal development forward" [3]. This idea reveals the importance of the individual approach in the pedagogical process. Individual psychological characteristics are a system of stable psychological signs that distinguish an individual from other people. These characteristics are manifested in human activity, communication, the pace of knowledge acquisition, and behavior.

Psychologist Boris Teplov interprets individual characteristics as psychological factors that determine the effectiveness of human activity. He considered abilities to be individual-psychological characteristics that serve a person's successful performance of a specific activity. In scientific literature, individual psychological characteristics are divided into the following main groups:

Temperament and its psychological and pedagogical significance in the process of learning a foreign language is that temperament occupies a special place in the structure of individual psychological characteristics of students. Temperament represents the dynamic aspects of the human psyche—that is, the emotional excitability, activity, speed, attitude toward external influences, and stable characteristics of behavior. Temperament significantly affects a person's pace of knowledge acquisition, sociability, emotional reaction, and activity in educational activities. Therefore, taking into account the temperamental characteristics of students in teaching a foreign language is one of the important factors in increasing pedagogical efficiency. The first scientific views on temperament were put forward by the ancient Greek physician and philosopher Hippocrates. Based on the balance of fluids in the human body, he distinguished four types of temperament. The Russian physiologist Ivan Pavlov studied temperament in connection with the characteristics of higher nervous activity and developed a scientific theory based on the strength, balance, and mobility of the nervous system. According to the scientist, the characteristics of human temperament are determined by the speed and

³. Lev Vygotsky. "Foundations of Psychology and Pedagogy". — Moscow, 1982.

stability of nervous processes. This approach serves as an important methodological basis for identifying the individual capabilities of students in pedagogy and psychology, and for the differentiated organization of the educational process. Temperament in psychology four main types are distinguished.

Students of the sanguine type are active, cheerful, communicative, and proactive. They adapt quickly to a new environment, tend to work in a team, and demonstrate high activity in dialogue, discussion, role-playing, and communicative exercises during foreign language lessons. Such students have strong speech activity and strive to express their thoughts freely in a foreign language. At the same time, since sanguine students may exhibit rapid distraction, the teacher must organize lessons in a dynamic and engaging manner.

Choleric students tend to be emotional, energetic, determined, and quick-witted. They actively undertake complex tasks, but may sometimes exhibit emotional instability or a sharp reaction. Choleric students effectively participate in debates, quick questions and answers, and creative assignments during foreign language lessons. At the same time, the teacher must focus on maintaining emotional balance, patience, and developing listening skills.

Students with a phlegmatic temperament are composed, patient, stable, and orderly. They tend to retain the knowledge they have acquired for a long time, even though they learn new material more slowly. Such students perform well in grammatical exercises, written assignments, and systematic independent work. In foreign language instruction, it is effective to allocate time appropriately for phlegmatic students and assign tasks that gradually become more complex.

Melancholic students are sensitive, sensitive, shy, and rich in inner experiences. They may often be embarrassed to speak in public, but demonstrate high responsibility and precision in individual matters. In learning a foreign language, melancholic students achieve success in written translation, text analysis, individual presentation, and independent assignments. In working with them, psychological support, positive motivation, and the creation of a stress-free environment are of great importance.

Organizing education taking into account temperament is one of the important requirements of student-centered education. This is because the way each student perceives, processes, and remembers information is different. Taking into account the characteristics of temperament in teaching a foreign language serves to develop students' communicative competence, increase learning motivation, and enhance educational efficiency.

Thus, taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of students is important in increasing the effectiveness of education. Temperament is an important component of students' individual psychological characteristics and directly affects their activity, sociability, pace of knowledge acquisition, and emotional stability during the foreign language learning process. Therefore, a modern teacher must organize lessons based on a differentiated and individual approach, taking into account the temperament types of students. In particular, taking into account psychological characteristics in teaching a foreign language serves to develop students' communicative competence.

List of used literature:

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